

Local Enhancement of Probability Due to Relaxation of Global Energy, Particle Number Constraints

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In classical statistical mechanics, one often has an ideal gas of identical particles subject to the global constraints of total energy E and total number of particles N . The energy constraint prevents each particle from being completely independent because if two particles each have $E/2$ of the energy, the rest must have 0 energy. This not only places interdependence on the particles, but also on regions of space because one cannot consider them as independent. In the case of particle number, this also places restrictions locally because if a certain proportion of particles are in states with $e_j > e_i$, one cannot locally place as many particles as one wants into state e_i .

We suggest that relaxing these constraints i.e. using new constraints $\sum_i e_i n(e_i) = E_{ave}$ and $\sum_i n(e_i) = N_{ave}$ are really approaches of enhancing local probability for e and n in e although the exact manner in which this enhancement appears must be determined. (Note: In the Fermi-Dirac case which is restrictive in n values, probability is inhibited. The enhancement is for bosons.)

Strict E and N Constraints

Physically one should have an ideal gas system with N particles and a total energy of E . This places restrictions on the system. First of all the particles cannot be independent because if two have energies $E/2$, the rest have energies of 0. This immediately breaks local spatial independence.

Thus one would ideally like to consider each particle as independent with probabilities to have any energy. Breaking global constraints automatically leads to a local equilibrium picture, i.e. within a little box dx by dx by dx as an equilibrium system because N tends to infinite. For example, one may have any energy in a local region which is really not physical and so there is an enhancement of probability at least for high energies. To see the exact form of the probability one may consider reaction balance. This applies for the whole system i.e. globally, but each subsystem is considered independent because there is no strict E_{total} constraint. One may retain the strict N constraint. Thus, there is a probability $p(e_i/T)$ to find a particle in an energy state e_i anywhere in space with e_i taking on any value (even one greater than E_{total}). Reaction balance for elastic scattering then yields:

$$E_1 + e_2 = e_3 + e_4 \quad ((1a)) \quad \text{and} \quad n(e_1)n(e_2) = n(e_3)n(e_4) \quad ((1b))$$

((1a)) and ((1b)) lead to: $n(e_i) = C(T) \exp(-e_i/T)$ where $\sum_{e_i} n(e_i) = E_{total}$ fixes T .

Here it is implicitly assumed that energy is the only information needed in the system. In other words, this is like tossing a die, there is a certain probability $p(e_i)$ to have a particle in e_i so $N p(e_i)$ represents the number of particles in e_i .

Given the form $\exp(-e_i/T)$ one may have energies $e_i > E$ which is unphysical, so these probabilities are inflated (they should be 0). It seems, however, that other probabilities are inflated because one may have $e_i = \text{high value} < E$, and these particles may exist at many different spatial locations at the same time again violating the sharp E total constraint. Thus we argue that relaxing the E_{total} constraint leads to local equilibrium, i.e. independence of particles because a high energy in one spatial region does not break the independence of particles in another spatial region. The price of this local equilibrium, however, is enhanced probabilities in e_i , we argue, especially for higher e_i values.

If one has N particles and wishes each particle to have any possible e_i value, one has the form:

$$Z = \left\{ \sum_i \exp(-e_i/T) \right\}^N \quad ((2))$$

$$\ln Z = N \ln \left\{ \sum_i \exp(-e_i/T) \right\} \quad ((3))$$

From ((3)) one may define various averages such as E_{ave} using derivatives of $\ln(Z)$ e.g. $d/d(1/T)$

Furthermore ((2)) shows that: $Z = \sum_{\text{all } E} \exp(-E/T)$ ((4)) where E is the N particle energy. ((4)) is called the canonical form.

The Question of Relaxing the Constraint on N

Given the two constraints E_{total} and N_{total} , if one relaxes E_{total} , mathematically one should be allowed to relax N_{total} . By examining ((4)) one might suggest:

$$Z = \sum_{E, N} \exp(-(E - uN)/T) \quad ((5))$$

Two parameters T and u are needed because there are now two constraint equations:

$$\sum_i e_i n(e_i) = E_{\text{ave}} = E_{\text{total}} \quad ((6a)) \quad \text{and} \quad \sum_i n(e_i) = N_{\text{ave}} = N_{\text{total}} \quad ((6b))$$

We argued in the above section that relaxing a constraint leads to an enhanced probability locally in e_i . For example one may see from ((2)) that one has various terms, each with N factors. If a certain proportion of these, say N_1 , have energy $> e_i$, then in a local region (and even globally) one cannot have more than $N - N_1$ particles in state e_i . Thus the restriction on N seems to restrict how many particles may go into state e_i locally. Relaxing the N constraint should allow for an enhanced probability of particles in state e_i . (This is a boson type condition.)

The relaxed E_{total} restriction leads to the Maxwell-Boltzmann probability $C(T)\exp(-e_i/T)$. Thus $N C(T)\exp(-e_i/T) = n(e_i)$. Relaxing the N constraint should possibly lead to an enhanced $n(e_i)$ which is no longer of the Maxwell-Boltzmann form.

Formally, one may calculate the effect of a relaxed N by calculating ((5)) using the single particle form i.e.

$$\ln(Z) = \sum_i \ln \left\{ \sum_n \exp(-\epsilon_i - u)n/T \right\} \quad ((7))$$

The Sum within {} is a geometric one with n ranging from 0 to infinite i.e.

$$\ln(Z) = \sum_i \ln \left\{ 1 / (1 - \exp(-\epsilon_i - u)/T) \right\} \quad ((8))$$

One may note that $z \frac{d}{dz} \ln(Z) = \sum_i \langle n(\epsilon_i) \rangle$ where $z = \exp(u/T)$. ((9))

Thus one has the Bose-Einstein distribution: $n(\epsilon_i) = 1 / \{ \exp(\epsilon_i - u)/T - 1 \}$ ((10))

In the Fermi-Dirac case one may only have $n=0,1$ leading to: $n(\epsilon_i) = 1 / \{ \exp(\epsilon_i - u)/T + 1 \}$ ((11))

The form ((10)) does not show the enhancement in probability by having more n in a state ϵ_i explicitly. Note by relaxing the restriction on E_{total} , one has more probability to have ϵ_i .

One may show that ((10)) is equivalent to the two body scattering balance:

$$E_1 + E_2 = E_3 + E_4 \quad ((12a)) \quad \text{and} \quad n(\epsilon_1)[1 + n(\epsilon_3)] n(\epsilon_2)[1 + n(\epsilon_4)] = n(\epsilon_3)[1 + n(\epsilon_1)] n(\epsilon_4)[1 + n(\epsilon_2)] \quad ((12b))$$

Thus there is an enhancement to scatter locally into states (in the boson case) which have more $n(\epsilon_i)$ already present. We argue that this is the n enhancement resulting from relaxing the N total constraint. The Fermi-Dirac case only allows $n=0,1$ and there is probability inhibition with $[1 + n(\epsilon_3)]$ etc being replaced with $[1 - n(\epsilon_3)]$ etc.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we note that an ideal gas is often described by a total E and total N. A fixed E does not allow for particle independence and local spatial region independence because if some particle at some place in the gas have energy of the order of E/2, this places severe restrictions on the energy available at local regions elsewhere. One may relax the E_{total} restriction by allowing all particles to have all possible energies at any local place. This means they may have energies above E_{total} or even if they are below this value, they may still be high in many different local regions leading to an overall violation of E_{total} . Using reaction balance:

$e_1 + e_2 = e_3 + e_4$ and $n(\epsilon_1)n(\epsilon_2) = n(\epsilon_3)n(\epsilon_4)$ leads to the Maxwell-Boltzmann form $C(T)\exp(-\epsilon_i/T)$ which increases the probability to have ϵ_i especially for high ϵ_i values.

Writing $\left\{ \sum_i \epsilon_i p(\epsilon_i) \right\}^N$ with $\exp(-\epsilon_i/T)$ is equivalent to $Z = \sum_E \exp(-E/T)$ where E is the system energy. This is called the canonical distribution.

Mathematically one may relax the restriction on N total which should enhance the probability to have n particles in an ϵ_i state. Formally one may write $Z = \sum_{E, N} \exp(-(E - uN)/T)$ and using $(E - uN) = \sum_i (\epsilon_i - u)n$ and the results of a geometric series find either the Fermi-Dirac or Bose-Einstein results. To see how the relaxation of N enhances probability (in the boson case) (it inhibits probability in the fermion case) one may consider the equivalent reaction

balance cases: $e_1 + e_2 = e_3 + e_4$ $n(e_1)[1 -/+ n(e_3)] n(e_2)[1 -/+ n(e_4)] = n(e_3)[1 -/+ n(e_1)] n(e_4)[1 -/+ n(e_2)]$ with - for fermions and + for bosons.

Thus we argue that relaxing constraints E,N leads to local enhanced probabilities for e_i and n_i , the number of particles in e_i (although for the Fermi-Dirac it inhibits).